

LINGUO-PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE TRANSLATION OF POLITICAL DISCOURSE ON THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Author: Baxromova Maftuna Baxrom qizi¹

Affiliation: Master's Student, International Nordic University¹

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19693699>

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of the linguo-pragmatic features of the use of artificial intelligence in the translation of political discourse on the example of Uzbek and English. It analyzes the main pragmatic aspects of political discourse, including implicit meaning, manipularity, and context dependence. The possibilities of AI-based translation tools in re-representing these features and existing linguistic problems are also examined. The results of the study show that although artificial intelligence provides speed and convenience in translation, there is still a need for the human factor in fully reflecting the deep pragmatic layers of political discourse. Also, this work serve to develop scientific and practical recommendations on the effective use of artificial intelligence in the fields of translation, discourse analysis and practical translation.

Keywords: Linguo-pragmatic, political discourse, implicit meaning, manipularity, artificial intelligence, human factor, pragmatic layers and translation.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the acceleration of the globalization process, political communication is gaining international importance. The translation of political relations between different states, official speeches and diplomatic speeches requires accuracy and agility. In this context, AI-based translation systems are widely used in the translation of political discourse. Political discourse has its own linguistic and pragmatic characteristics, in which the elements of implicit meaning, ideological loading, manipulative strategies and influence on the audience occupy an important place. Communicating such features from one language to another in a correct and adequate way is one of the complex issues of interpreting. Cultural and pragmatic differences play an important role, especially in translation between Uzbek and English. The purpose of this study is to identify the linguo - pragmatic features of the use of artificial intelligence in the translation of political discourse, to analyze its capabilities and limitations on the example of Uzbek and English.

The issues of political discourse and its translation have been studied by many scholars. In Particular, Teun A. van Dijk analyzed political discourse as a communicative process related to ideology and power. He argues that political discourse is a means of influencing social consciousness through language.¹

¹ van Dijk, T. A. Political Discourse and Ideology.

Norman Fairclough, on the other hand, has explored in depth the social and pragmatic aspects of political discourse within critical discourse analysis, basing the connection between language and power.²

In translation, however, Mona Baker emphasizes the importance of context and discourse in translating political texts. He shows in translation the need to ensure not only linguistic, but also pragmatic compatibility.³

In recent years, artificial intelligence-based translation technologies have developed widely, notably neural translation systems. Research by Philipp Koehn notes that the efficiency of automatic translation has increased, while problems with conveying complex discursive and pragmatic meanings remain.⁴

At the same time, modern studies show that artificial intelligence has not yet achieved complete perfection in translating metaphors, euphemisms and implicit meanings in political discourse.

And let's look through some of the examples:

1. Example of implicit meaning (political discourse):

"We will restore stability and protect our national interests."

Artificial intelligence translation (simple):

"Biz barqarorlikni tiklaymiz va milliy manfaatlarimizni himoya qilamiz."

Analysis:

Here, the phrase "restore stability" implicitly implies that there is a problem or instability in the country. Artificial intelligence translation is grammatically correct, but does not deeply reveal a hidden political context (such as criticism or a reference to crisis).

2. Euphemism(softening):

"We are considering a military intervention."

Artificial intelligence translation (simple):

"Biz harbiy aralashuvni ko'rib chiqmoqdamiz."

Analysis:

"Military intervention" is euphemism that can actually denote war or military action. The translation is correct, but artificial intelligence does not explain the political Mitigation Function of this phrase.

3. Cultural-pragmatic discrepancy:

"We will build a New Uzbekistan together."

Artificial intelligence translation (simple):

"Yangi O'zbekistonni birgalikda quramiz."

Analysis:

In Uzbek, the phrase has a strong ideological and emotional load. In English, it sounds a little more formal and neutral. Hence, artificial intelligence conveys content, but the emotional-pragmatic effect is not fully maintained.

The cited examples suggest that artificial intelligence provides lexical and grammatical accuracy in translation, but has limitations in fully conveying implicit meaning, euphemism, and cultural-pragmatic loading inherent in political discourse. For this reason, the participation of the human translator in the translation of such texts remains important.

A number of methods have also been used. These are:

² Fairclough, N. Language and Power.

³ Baker, M. In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation

⁴ Koehn, P. Neural Machine Translation./ Hatim, B., Mason, I. Discourse and the Translator.

- a. **Comparative analysis method**-political speeches in Uzbek and English and their translations using artificial intelligence were compared.
- b. **Discursive analysis**-the pragmatic characteristics of political speeches (implicit meaning, manipulability, context) were determined and studied how they were reflected in translation.
- c. **Content-analysis**-linguistic units used in political texts (metaphor, euphemism, stylistic means) were systematically analyzed.
- d. **Descriptive method**-general features and problems of translation of artificial intelligence were described.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study show that the use of artificial intelligence in the translation of political discourse is gaining importance in modern translatability. Artificial intelligence-based translation tools allow for quickness, convenience, and short processing of large volumes of text. It is especially effective in international political communication. At the same time, political discourse is characterized by its complex linguistic-pragmatic features - implicit meaning, manipularity, metaphoricity, and cultural connotations. During the study, it was discovered that artificial intelligence often takes a superficial approach to translating these aspects and cannot fully deliver pragmatic content. As a result, the impact force of translation decreases in some cases. Analysis using the example of Uzbek and English also confirms that the differences between languages and cultures play an important role in the translation of political speech. Artificial intelligence, on the other hand, does not always adequately account for these differences. While artificial intelligence in general is effective as an auxiliary tool in political discourse translation, the involvement of the human interpreter is necessary to ensure a high level of linguo-pragmatic accuracy. In the future, it will become an important task to expand the possibilities of more accurately representing the deep layers of meaning of political speech through the improvement of artificial intelligence technologies.

REFERENCES

1. van Dijk, T. A. (1997). *Discourse as structure and process*. Sage Publications.
2. van Dijk, T. A. (1998). *Ideology: A multidisciplinary approach*. Sage Publications.
3. Fairclough, N. (2001). *Language and power* (2nd ed.). Longman.
4. Baker, M. (2018). *In other words: A coursebook on translation* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
5. Koehn, P. (2020). *Neural machine translation*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Hatim, B., & Mason, I. (1997). *The translator as communicator*. Routledge.
7. Newmark, P. (1988). *A textbook of translation*. Prentice Hall.